

A new chelating resin selective for Cu^{II} and Hg^{II}

D. K. Singh*, R. Gupta and Anuradha Singh

Analytical Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, H. B. Technological Institute, Kanpur-208 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dhruvks123@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 29 November 2005, revised 8 May 2006, accepted 11 May 2006

Abstract : A chelating resin based on catechol-formaldehyde copolymer containing 'oxime' functional group has been synthesized. Mercury(II) and copper(II) were separated in presence of other metal ions with this resin.

Keywords : Chelating resin, copper(II) ion, mercury(II) ion.

In continuation to our earlier work on the chelating resins¹, this study describes a simple pathway for the synthesis of a new chelating resin containing 8-HQ as chelating groups. The chelating resin has been characterized on the basis of nitrogen estimation, sorption capacity and FTIR analysis. The rate of sorption, breakthrough capacity and distribution coefficients for metal ions were investigated. The mini-columns of resin have been demonstrated for the quantitative separation and remediation of water containing Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Results and discussion

The sorption capacity of chelating resin for Cu^{II} is 0.67 mmol/g. The chelating resin also shows a little ion exchange capacity for Na^+ (0.2 mmol/g). This seems due to exchange between H^+ ions of OH groups of catechol/8-HQ and Na^+ ions. The content of 8-HQ in the chelating resin was estimated 15.3%, on the basis of nitrogen determination of resin and comparing it with that of initial 8-HQ.

IR study : The FTIR spectrum of chelating resin showed a broad absorption band in the region 3100–3400 cm^{-1} , which is evident due to -OH stretching in chelate compound. The absorption peak at 1602 cm^{-1} was due to the presence of C=N group stretching vibration in the ring. The peaks at 1553, 1503 and 1436 cm^{-1} were due to aromatic ring. The peak at 1218 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-O stretching vibrations of catechol. Thus it is evident that the chelating resin contains 8-HQ.

The rate copper(II) sorption was quite high and was almost 95% complete within 30 min; however, equilibrium was attained in 50 min. The high rate of sorption

may be explained on the basis of Cu-8-HQ complex formation. The sorption capacity of the chelating resin was found to be 0.67 mmol/g.

The breakthrough curves for Hg^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} revealed that as many as 64 bed volumes (BV, 1 BV = 10 ml) of Hg^{2+} (corresponding to 0.64 mmol of Hg) can be passed through the chelating resin column without any trace being detected if the effluent. Similarly, for Cu^{II} occurred after 62 BV (corresponding to 0.62 mmol of Cu), Co^{II} after 60 BV (corresponding to 0.60 mmol of Co) and for Zn^{II} after 44 bed volumes (corresponding to 0.44 mmol of Zn). The distribution coefficients of Hg^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Fe^{III} , Al^{III} , La^{III} , Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} were determined in the pH range 1–7. The K_d values increase with increase in pH. The K_d values revealed that Hg^{II} and Cu^{II} are strongly sorbed on the chelating resin; Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Th^{IV} and Zn^{II} only partially while Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , La^{III} , Al^{III} , Pb^{II} and Zr^{IV} are scarcely sorbed at pH 1. The high selectivity (K_d) of the chelating resin for certain metal ions seems due to more stable complexes of these metal ions with 8-HQ. Separation of metal ions were carried out and the recoveries were quantitative within the range of experimental error ($\pm 1\%$).

Recovery of Hg^{2+} or Cu^{2+} and effect of diverse ions : One liter of water sample (pH ~ 1) containing Hg^{II} (200–600 μg) or Cu^{II} (50–600 μg) and foreign metal ions (Pb, Zr, Al, La and Mn) was passed through the resin bed at a flow rate of 5 ml/ml. The foreign metal ions were not sorbed at pH 1. The sorbed Hg^{II} and Cu^{II} were quantitatively eluted with 30 ml of 2 M HNO_3 .

Experimental

Catechol, formaldehyde and 8-hydroxyquinoline (B.D.H., India) were used. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. A Systronic 335 pH meter and Shimadzu 8201 PC were used for pH measurements and FTIR spectrum (KBr method), respectively. Nitrogen was determined using Heraeus-Carlo-Ebra 1108 analyzer.

Synthesis of chelating resin : The chelating resin was synthesized by mixing catechol (0.1 mmol), formaldehyde (0.2 mmol) and 8-HQ (0.1 mmol) in the presence of 2 M H₂SO₄ (50 ml) as catalyst. The reaction mixture was heated at 60–70 °C in a water bath with constant stirring for 24 h. The separated resinous product was washed with demineralized water, dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C. Finally, the material was ground and sieved to 60–100 mesh.

The rate of sorption was studied by shaking 0.1 g of the chelating resin with 20 ml of metal ion solution. After different time intervals the contents of the flasks were filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper and the amount of unadsorbed metal ions in the filtrate was estimated by EDTA titration. The breakthrough curves of Hg^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Zn^{II} were studied by passing 0.001 M solution of each metal ion (pH ~ 7) through a glass column packed with 1 g (0.9 ml) chelating resin. The flow rate was maintained 0.5 ml/min. Portions of dried resin (0.1 g) were equilibrated with 20 ml solution containing 0.1 mmol

of metal ions and NaOAc-HOAc or NaCl-HCl buffer solutions for 6 h in a mechanical shaker at 25 ± 1 °C. After equilibration the resin was separated by filtration. The filtrate was analyzed for metal ions by EDTA titration. The distribution coefficients (K_d) were calculated from the following equation :

$$K_d \text{ (ml g}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{Amount of metal ion in resin g}^{-1}}{\text{Amount of metal ion in solution ml}^{-1}}$$

Chromatographic separations : A chromatographic glass column (i.d. 0.4 mm) was filled with the slurry of resin (2 g), washed with demineralised water and then the mixture of metal ions was introduced into the column and allowed to be sorbed. The sorbed metal ions were eluted separately using appropriate eluents and analysed. The flow rate was maintained ~0.2 ml through the column process.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Director, H. B. Technological Institute, Kanpur, for facilities.

References

1. D. K. Singh and M. Srivastava, *Sep. Purf. Technol.*, 2005, **45**, 1; *Chem. Anal. Warsaw*, 2005, **50**, 377; *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 2005, **40**, 2053; *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 2006 (in press); D. K. Singh and R. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 447.